

A Study of the Complex Compounds of N-Benzenesulphonyl Glycine with Some Metal Ions:

Part VII. Benzenesulphonyl α - and β -Alanines

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N-Benzenesulphonyl α - and β -alanines ($R^\alpha H_2$ and $R^\beta H_2$) form complex compounds with Cu(II), Ag(I), Zn(II), Cd(II), and Hg(II). With Cu(II), compounds isolated are $Cu(R^\alpha H)(OH)(H_2O)$, $Cu(R^\alpha H)_2(H_2O)$ (CH_3COCH_3), $Cu(R^\alpha H)_2$, $Na_2CuR^\alpha_2$ and $Cu(R^\beta H)_2$ but with Ag(I) and Hg(II), both $R^\alpha H_2$ and $R^\beta H_2$ give same type of complexes Ag_2R , $AgRH$, $Hg(RH)(OH)(H_2O)$ and Na_2HgR_2 . Zn(II) and Cd(II) are found to form bis-compounds but $R^\alpha H_2$ also gives another Cd(II) complex $Cd(R^\alpha H)(OH)(H_2O)$. $Cu(R^\alpha H)_2(H_2O)(CH_3COCH_3)$ is a weak dibasic acid. By potentiometric titration at constant ionic strength ($\mu = 0.5$), pK_2 and pK_1 are evaluated by projection strip method and found to be 4.7 and 7.1. But $Cu(R^\beta H)_2$ decomposes on addition of alkali. Magnetic data and spectra of Cu(II) complexes are also recorded and discussed.

As chelating agents N-benzenesulphonyl glycine¹ and its nitro-derivatives^{2,3} gave interesting results that led the present authors to study the reaction of N-benzenesulphonyl α - and β -alanines ($R^\alpha H_2$ and $R^\beta H_2$) with different metal cations.

Cu(II) complex compounds isolated are $Cu(R^\alpha H)(OH)(H_2O)$, $[Cu(R^\alpha H)(OH)]_2$, $Cu(R^\alpha H)_2(H_2O)$ (CH_3COCH_3), $Cu(R^\alpha H)_2$, $Na_2CuR^\alpha_2$ and $Cu(R^\beta H)_2$. The complex $Cu(R^\beta H)_2$ decomposes on treating with alkali so the sodium salt could not be isolated. A preliminary note⁴ on Cu(II) chelates has been published. With Ag(I) and Hg(II), both $R^\alpha H_2$ and $R^\beta H_2$ give same type of complexes e.g., Ag_2R , $AgRH$, $Hg(RH)(OH)(H_2O)$ and Na_2HgR_2 . Two compounds $Cd(R^\alpha H)(OH)(H_2O)$ and $Cd(R^\alpha H)_2$ are isolated as reaction products between Cd(II) and $R^\alpha H_2$, but only one compound, $Cd(R^\beta H)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ from $R^\beta H_2$. Zn(II) is found to form bis-compound in each case.

The compound $Cu(R^\alpha H)_2(H_2O)(CH_3COCH_3)$ is a weak dibasic acid. By potentiometric titration at constant ionic strength ($\mu = 0.5$) pK_2 and pK_1 are evaluated by projection strip method⁵. Magnetic susceptibility of all Cu(II) complexes have been determined at room temperature and the electronic spectra of aqueous solutions of $Cu(R^\alpha H)_2(H_2O)$ (CH_3COCH_3), $Cu(R^\alpha H)_2$, $Na_2CuR^\alpha_2$ and $Cu(R^\beta H)_2$ have also been measured.

1. N. N. Ghosh and M. N. Majumdar, *This Journal*, 1963, **40**, 945.
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5. F. J. C. Rossotti and H. Rossotti, 'The Determination of stability constants', McGraw-Hill Book Company Inc., New York, 1961.

EXPERIMENTAL

N-benzenesulphonyl α - and β -alanines were prepared following the methods stated in the literature^{6,7} [Found : Eqv. Wt., 227.8 and 226.7; Calc. 229]. They are soluble in ethanol, acetone, etc., and sparingly so in cold water.

A. *Complex compounds of Cu(II)*

Freshly prepared CuO in aqueous suspension was treated with $R^{\alpha}H_2$ in the ratio 1 : 1. The mixture was heated on steam bath for several hours when CuO partially dissolved, forming a blue solution. It was filtered and the filtrate was allowed to evaporate on water bath. Blue crystals which separated were collected, washed with acetone and air dried. [Found : Cu, 19.40; N, 4.39; $Cu(R^{\alpha}H)(H_2O)(OH)$ requires Cu, 19.45; N, 4.29%]. When $R^{\beta}H_2$ was similarly treated, needle shaped blue crystals of $Cu(R^{\beta}H)_2$ separated. These were collected and air dried. [Found : Cu, 12.20; N, 5.36; $Cu(R^{\beta}H)_2$ requires Cu, 12.23; N, 5.39%]. On heating $Cu(R^{\alpha}H)(OH)(H_2O)$ at 110° for few hrs, lost one molecule of water (loss found, 5.73; Calc. 5.51%) yielding a light blue insoluble compound, possibly having the diol bridge structure. [Found : Cu, 20.46; N, 4.49; $[Cu(R^{\alpha}H)(OH)]_2$ requires Cu, 20.58; N, 4.53%]. The compound $Cu(R^{\alpha}H)(OH)(H_2O)$ with $R^{\alpha}H_2$ in aqueous ethanol (in the ratio 1 : 1) was refluxed on steam bath for one hour. A deep blue solution was obtained. The clear filtrate was concentrated on water bath and finally in vacuum over H_2SO_4 . The blue residue on trituration with redistilled acetone yielded a blue powder which was washed several times with acetone and was air dried. [Found : Cu, 10.56; N, 4.70; CH_3COCH_3 , 9.83; $Cu(R^{\alpha}H)_2(H_2O)(CH_3COCH_3)$ requires Cu, 10.67; N, 4.70; CH_3COCH_3 , 9.74%]. On heating this compound for several hours at 110° , the loss in weight corresponded one molecule of water and one molecule of acetone (loss found, 12.67; Calc. 12.77%) yielding a greenish blue hygroscopic compound. [Found : Cu, 12.20; N, 5.29; $Cu(R^{\alpha}H)_2$ requires Cu, 12.23; N, 5.39%].

The compound $Cu(R^{\alpha}H)_2(H_2O)(CH_3COCH_3)$ when treated with cold dilute NaOH solution (in the ratio 1 : 2), gave a deep blue solution which was concentrated in vacuum over H_2SO_4 and solid NaOH. The indigo blue crystals that separated were washed with ethanol and dried in a vacuum desiccator over NaOH. [Found : Cu, 11.10; N, 4.86; Na, 8.27; $Na_2CuR^{\alpha}_2$ requires Cu, 11.27; N, 4.97; Na, 8.16%].

B. *Complex compounds of Ag(I) and Hg(II)*

When $AgNO_3$ or $Hg(NO_3)_2$ solution containing RH_2 was treated with alkali, precipitation of complex compounds took place at pH 2.5-3.5. They were collected and air dried. Composition of the complexes were Ag_2R and $Hg(RH)(OH)(H_2O)$. Analytical data are stated in Table I.

Freshly precipitated Ag_2O and an aqueous solution of RH_2 taken in the ratio 1 : 2 was heated on a water bath for several hours and then filtered hot. On cooling white crystals were obtained. These were collected, washed with ethanol and air dried. Composition

6. S. G. Hedin, *Ber.*, 1890, **23**, 3196.

7. H. V. Pechmann, *Annalen.*,⁸ 1891, **264**, 289.

was found to be AgRH. The complex compounds of the type Na_2HgR_2 were prepared by heating freshly prepared HgO with an aqueous solution of the sodium salt of RH_2 . On concentrating the filtrate white compounds separated in both cases. Analyses of the complexes are shown in Table I.

C. Complex compounds of Zn(II) and Cd(II)

By treating freshly precipitated ZnO with $\text{R}^\alpha\text{H}_2$ or R^βH_2 only *bis*-compounds $\text{Zn}(\text{RH})_2$ were isolated. On the other hand Cd(II) complexes isolated were $\text{Cd}(\text{R}^\alpha\text{H})(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ and $\text{Cd}(\text{R}^\beta\text{H})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. However the *bis*-compound $\text{Cd}(\text{R}^\alpha\text{H})_2$ was prepared by warming a mixture of CdO and $\text{R}^\alpha\text{H}_2$ (in the ratio 1 : 2.5) in aqueous suspension. The clear filtrate was allowed to evaporate when crystals of $\text{Cd}(\text{R}^\alpha\text{H})_2$ separated. Analyses are shown in the Table I.

TABLE I

Compound	% Metal		% Nitrogen		% Sodium		% of loss at 110°	
	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
$\text{Hg}(\text{R}^\alpha\text{H})(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})$	43.51	43.20	3.20	3.02				
$\text{Hg}(\text{R}^\beta\text{H})(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})$	43.70	43.20	3.14	3.02				
$\text{Na}_2\text{HgR}^\alpha_2$	28.20	28.63	3.85	4.00	6.53	6.57		
$\text{Na}_2\text{HgR}^\beta_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	26.20	25.94	3.70	3.62	5.92	5.96	9.31	9.33
$\text{Na}_2\text{HgR}^\beta_2$			4.15	4.00				
$\text{Ag}_2\text{R}^\alpha$	48.42	48.75	3.25	3.16				
$\text{Ag}_2\text{R}^\beta$	48.70	48.75	3.12	3.16				
$\text{AgR}^\alpha\text{H}$	32.06	32.15	4.21	4.17				
AgR^βH	32.20	32.15	4.29	4.17				
$\text{Zn}(\text{R}^\alpha\text{H})_2$	12.82	12.53	5.23	5.38				
$\text{Zn}(\text{R}^\beta\text{H})_2$	12.39	12.53	5.26	5.38				
$\text{Cd}(\text{R}^\alpha\text{H})(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})$	30.50	29.94	3.90	3.73				
$\text{Cd}(\text{R}^\alpha\text{H})_2$	19.60	19.78	4.92	4.93				
$\text{Cd}(\text{R}^\beta\text{H})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	18.86	18.60	4.57	4.63			5.99	5.96
$\text{Cd}(\text{R}^\beta\text{H})_2$			4.85	4.93				

The potentiometric titration of an aqueous solution of $\text{Cu}(\text{R}^\alpha\text{H})_2 \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{CH}_3\text{COCH}_3)$, containing requisite amount of NaClO_4 to keep the ionic strength constant ($\mu = 0.5$), was made with a standard NaOH solution at room temperature 30°. The average number ($\bar{n}\text{H}$) of ionisable hydrogen attached to the molecule was calculated and the $\bar{n}\text{H}$ values were plotted against the corresponding pH values. pK_2 and pK_1 were then evaluated by the projection strip method and are found to be 4.7 and 7.1 respectively.

The magnetic susceptibility measurements of Cu(II) complexes were made and data obtained after diamagnetic corrections are shown in Table II. Electronic spectra of water soluble Cu(II) complexes were measured in aqueous solutions and the data are included in Table II. Data on electronic spectra of ligands R^*H_2 and $R^{\#}H_2$ are also included.

TABLE II

Compound	μ_p in B.M.	λ_{max}^{eg} in $m\mu$	log ϵ
$Cu(R^*H)(OH)(H_2O)$	2.07		
$\{Cu(R^*H)(OH)\}_2$	1.92		
$Cu(R^*H)_2(H_2O)(CH_3COCH_3)$	1.39	780	1.32
		330	1.78
		272	3.13
		265	3.24
		258	3.21
		235	3.50
$Cu(R^{\#}H)_2$	1.40	780	1.36
		325	1.85
		272	3.13
		265	3.24
		258	3.20
		235	3.50
$Na_2CuR_2^*$	1.80	680	1.71
		280	2.99
		260	2.12
		223	4.09
$Cu(R^{\#}H)_2$	1.42	780	1.27
		320	1.24
		265	3.24
		222	4.09
R^*H_2		272	2.80
		265	2.88
		259	2.77
		234	2.19
$R^{\#}H_2$		272	3.32
		265	2.95
		259	2.78
		202	3.18

DISCUSSION

In the cases of $\text{Cu}(\text{R}^\alpha\text{H})(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})$, $[\text{Cu}(\text{R}^\alpha\text{H})(\text{OH})]_2$ and $\text{Na}_2\text{CuR}^\alpha_2$ the magnetic moments have normal values. On the other hand the subnormal values were found in the cases of $\text{Cu}(\text{R}^\alpha\text{H})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{CH}_3\text{COCH}_3)$, $\text{Cu}(\text{R}^\alpha\text{H})_2$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{R}^\beta\text{H})_2$. These latter moments are closely comparable to $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$ salts of organic fatty acids⁸. It is interesting to mention here that on ionisation of imido-hydrogen of $\text{Cu}(\text{R}^\alpha\text{H})_2$ to $\text{CuR}^\alpha_2^{2-}$ the normal magnetic moment values were observed.

The electronic spectra of aqueous solution of $\text{Cu}(\text{R}^\alpha\text{H})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{CH}_3\text{COCH}_3)$, $\text{Cu}(\text{R}^\alpha\text{H})_2$, $\text{Na}_2\text{CuR}^\alpha_2$, and $\text{Cu}(\text{R}^\beta\text{H})_2$ have been measured. Almost all $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$ compounds are blue or green and absorption bands are found in the region 600–900 $\text{m}\mu$ ⁹. In the present cases absorption bands in the said region have also been observed. Absorption peaks in the ultraviolet region, having high molar extinction values, are undoubtedly due to ligand molecules.

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